

**OUR 4TH NEWSLETTER
IS HERE!**

Dear friends, partners and colleagues,

We hope you are having a smooth start into 2023! The last year has been busy at e-SAFE, and we're happy to share our fourth newsletter with you.

In the last months we have been present at several events to spread the message that it is important to apply renovation solutions that combine energy-efficient and anti-seismic retrofitting measures, especially since many European countries are strongly prone to earthquakes.

Additionally, we were looking for multi-storey non historical buildings that are located in earthquake-prone areas in Europe and in need of renovation which would serve us as virtual pilots. We received numerous applications and two were selected: a school building in Timisoara and a residential building in Bucharest. Over the next months, e-SAFE will work with local partners to deliver a detailed renovation project through a co-design process with residents, covering architectural, energy-efficient and anti-seismic renovation solutions tailor-made and other free renovation advice to achieve an eco-friendly, earthquake-safe building. Get to know our virtual pilots [here](#)

We wish you a happy reading and feel free to get in touch with us for anything related to the e-SAFE Project!

Sunny regards from Catania,

Giuseppe Margani & the e-SAFE team

Discover the e-SAFE pilots in Timișoara and Bucharest!

Last April, e-SAFE launched a call looking for multi-storey non-historical buildings that are in earthquake-prone areas in Europe and in need of renovation. The call was open to building owners or building managers, public or private entities that administer social housing or public buildings, as well as real estate brokers. The benefits from working with e-SAFE are numerous: receiving a survey and 3D models of the building, an energy audit, energy analysis, and structural simulations, a detailed e-SAFE based renovation project through a co-design process with residents, covering architectural, energy-efficient and anti-seismic renovation solutions tailor-made and other free renovation advice to achieve an eco-friendly, earthquake-safe building.

The public call for expression of interest was a two-stage process: in the first stage, applicants had to express their interest and fill in a form with the main features of the building. The information provided made possible a first check of the suitability of the building to the e-SAFE technical requirements. A total of 32 applications of buildings have been submitted by 20 applicants.

In the second stage of the call, the owners of the selected buildings were asked to provide more technical information, such as building plans, photos of all fronts, energy performance certificate, and a more detailed form about building structure and HVACs, allowing a more thorough final selection of the two virtual pilots. In September 2022, after this second round of selection, the experts of the e-SAFE consortium selected the two buildings that seemed most consistent with the requirements.

And the winners are...

Sports Banatul Highschool (Timisoara) with local partners AIIR (Romanian Association of Building Services Engineers) and Polytechnic University of Timișoara

The pilot is a school located in Timisoara, near the Polytechnic University and its campus. It was last renovated in 2006, where windows and exterior doors were replaced. Its structure is composed of reinforced concrete, with hollow bricks and double glazing. It is connected to the district heating system, with radiators as main heating terminal. Hot water production is centralised and does not have any cooling system or terminal.

Residential building in the Municipality of Bucharest with local partner AMCCRS (Administrația Municipală pentru Consolidarea Clădirilor cu Risc Seismic)

This pilot is a 1872 m² residential building located in Bucharest, and composed of 20 residential units. Since its construction, the building, has never undergone any renovation works.

The structure is composed of reinforced concrete, with solid bricks, single glazing and PVC window frames. It benefits from a mixed heating system, with radiators as main heating terminal. It has an autonomous cooling system using fan coils.

What are the next steps?

Partners and local organisations will collect all necessary information about the buildings (geometric, thermal, structural...), and investigate the requirements in place in Romania for seismic and energy renovation, as well as the estimated renovation costs depending on the local market. The next step will be to develop an initial set of configurations for both projects, including structural and thermal solutions.

How will end users be involved?

Families and students will have the chance to take part in the co-design process. They will learn more about the project and about existing local best practices and will support with collecting all necessary data. They will also have the chance to discuss the proposed structural and thermal configurations together with local experts, before presenting to the public.

Interview with Venera Pavone, Urban Planner at UNICT

Vera will lead the e-SAFE co-design process on the ground in Timisoara and Bucharest with building owners and citizens.

You will be leading e-SAFE efforts on the ground in Timisoara and Bucharest to co-design an energy efficient, seismic-safe renovation project together with building owners and occupants over a period of several months. This is a huge task! Can you tell us a bit about what the process will look like, and explain your role in all of this?

The word "co-design" refers to a participatory, co-creative, and open design process where the building's end users share their ideas, needs, and aspirations with the technical experts so that together they can identify the best solutions framed within a common background. It will be a mutual learning process that involves all the people who have a stake in the building. This kind of process requires a long time to be effective. As a result, the activities will be scheduled over a period of three months and arranged to address all issues related to the building's deep renovation (thermal systems, structure, architectural issues, etc.) in a way that is understandable to everyone. As an expert in participatory processes, I am responsible to ensure high quality and democratic governance of the process, to build confidence and trust in decision making, to generate a greater understanding of issues, concerns, priorities, and solutions among stakeholders, to increase mutual learning through the sharing of information, data, and experiences, to reach agreements in a collaborative manner and of course, to create enthusiasm in being part of it. Yes, it is a huge task, but it is fun!

Read the full interview here!

Policy briefing: ensuring safe and energy efficient buildings through the revised EPBD

How to implement integrated seismic and energy efficiency renovations through the revised EPBD

The recast EPBD, currently in the last leg of negotiations between the European Parliament and Council, intends to increase the rate and depth of renovation and introduces important provisions to phase-out the worst-performing buildings and to tackle fuel poverty. However, energy performance is not the only challenge faced by the European building stock. About 50% of European territory is earthquake prone. In the last 50 years, earthquakes in Europe have caused over 36.000 deaths and around 1.4 million people becoming homeless.

The e-SAFE project focuses on highly seismic countries in Europe, such as Albania, Greece, Turkey, Italy, Croatia and Romania, where a destructive earthquake would render investments in energy-efficient renovations unsustainable from a social, economic and environmental point of view. These countries therefore need energy renovation actions that are strategically combined with seismic retrofitting by prioritizing the worst-performing buildings in terms of energy performance and structural safety.

This policy briefing suggests practical ways that the proposed EPBD recast can strategically support the uptake of seismic renovations alongside energy efficiency in the EU, in order to ensure concrete implementation of seismic safety measures where it is needed most.

Read the policy briefing
here

e-SAFE Events

e-SAFE at EUSEW 2022

The 2022 edition of the European **Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW)** under the theme “*Going green and digital for Europe’s energy transition*” took place 26-30 September in Brussels.

In this stimulating context, e-SAFE was one of the projects selected to have its own stand at the **Networking Village!**

Our onsite team, composed of UNICT, BPIE and Moverim, explained the main features, objectives, and results of the projects and engaged new potential stakeholders, by also networking with partners from the other projects on display.

The **Energy Fair** was an incredible opportunity to share our innovative ideas and to find many potentials interested parties towards the urgent issues of energy efficiency and seismic safety!

In the context of EUSEW, e-SAFE also co-hosted a cluster event on deep energy renovation of residential buildings with seismic strengthening approaches – included in the **Sustainable Energy Days program** – with the H2020 project ProGETone, where experts from both projects discussed outcomes and results in different presentations and a final roundtable.

[Find out more about the event](#)

e-SAFE at New European Bauhaus Festival

From 8 to 12 June 2022 took place the very first edition of the **New European Bauhaus Festival**, promoted by the European Commission. The Festival was an opportunity to bring together a large audience with the aim of promoting dialogue on a **sustainable, inclusive and beautiful future**.

The team composed of Moverim, UNICT and BPIE interacted with visitors, explaining the main features, objectives and results of the projects, and engaged new potential stakeholders, while also networking with partners from the other projects on display.

The fair, although in its first edition, was quite successful and gave the e-SAFE project a chance to be introduced to the European and Brussels audiences!

Know more!

**Check out our
reel on Instagram!**

Future Events

Central and Eastern European Energy Efficiency Forum – 23-26 May 2023

This year, the C4E Forum will be taking place between the 23rd and 26th of May 2023, in the central location of Šamorín near Bratislava, Slovakia. Due to the current geo-political situation and timing of the C4E Forum 2023, taking place after a winter with high energy prices across Europe, the main topics that will be addressed at the event are energy security, the rebuilding of Ukraine and EU policy (REPowerEU and Fit-for-55 package). The Forum is organized by the Renovate Europe Campaign (REC), with the support of their national partner Buildings for the Future.

More information [here](#)

World Conference on Timber Engineering – 19-22 June 2023

The 2023 edition of WCTE will be held in Oslo, Norway and will be open to all scientists, academicians, young researchers, business delegates and students from all over the world. In the planning of WCTE 2023, the organisers kept up the emphasis on research and exploration within wood mechanics and timber structures.

e-SAFE partner NMBU applied to present two papers at the Conference on *Cyclic Tests On An Innovative Friction Dissipative Device For Seisim Retrofit With Clt Panels* and on *Asymmetric Friction Connections (AFC): temperature dependent probabilistic friction model*.

[To know more](#)

World Conference on
Timber Engineering
Oslo 2023

e-SAFE stakeholder community: seismic and energy efficiency renovations for all of Europe

If you'd like to stay abreast on all news related to e-SAFE and seismic renovations in general, we invite you to join our **e-SAFE stakeholder community** on LinkedIn. You will also be able to share any publication, event or news with the rest of the members and engage in various discussions.

Join the discussion on
LinkedIn!

Thanks for your attention!

Be sure to **follow us** on **Social Media** to keep upon all the latest **e-SAFE news!**

Partners

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